

Overall study design

Title of the study	Vendor-dependent mobile phase contaminants affect neutral lipid analysis in lipidomics protocols		
Document creation date	05/09/2024	Corresponding Email	jeff.smith@carleton.ca
Principle investigator	Jeffrey C. Smith	Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?	Untargeted
Institution	Carleton University	Clinical	No

Lipid extraction

Extraction method	2-phase system	2-phase system	Bligh&Dyer
Derivatization	-	Were internal standards added prior extraction?	No
pH adjustment	Acetic acid		

Analytical platform

Ionization additives	Ammonium formate	MS Level	MS2
Number of separation dimensions	One dimension	Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)	1.3
Separation type 1	LC	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS2	High resolution
Separation mode 1 (liquid)	RP	Resolution at m/z 200 at MS2	27286
Detector	Mass spectrometer	Mass accuracy in ppm at MS2	10
MS type	QTOF	Recording mode of raw data at MS2	Centroid mode
MS vendor	Agilent	Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	No
Ion source	ESI		

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Quality control	No
Type of Blanks	Solvent blank		

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	No
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Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	Yes	Summary data	Identification data
Link to repository / ID to entry	doi:10.25345/C5N29PJ3D	Raw data upload	Yes
Are metadata available?	Yes	Additional comments	Raw data files are converted to the mzML open source format from the vendor (Agilent) .d files

Sample Descriptions

Bovine Liver Extract / Bos Taurus / Tissues (e.g., liver, heart, brain)

Perfusion	No	Additives	None
Provided information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Storage time (month)	Were samples stored under inert gas?	Yes
Temperature handling original sample	-20 °C	Additional preservation methods	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Biobank samples	No
Storage temperature	-20 °C	Sample homogenization	No
Storage time (month)	24		

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Cer	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	No
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator
Fragment name	[M-H ₂ O+H] ⁺		
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

1) Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

2) CE[M+NH₄]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	CE	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	No
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH ₄] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator
Fragment name -FA1(+HO)-Cholesterol(35)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

2) CE[M+NH₄]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

3) DG[M+NH₄]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	DG	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	No
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH ₄] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator
Fragment name -(H ₂ O+NH ₃ ,35)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

3) DG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

4) LPC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPC	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	No
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator
Fragment name	HG(PC,184)		
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

4) LPC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

5) LPE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPE	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	No
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator
Fragment name	-HG(PE,141)		
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

5) LPE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

6) PC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	No
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator
Fragment name	HG(PC,184)		
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

6) PC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

7) PE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	No
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator
Fragment name	-HG(PE,141)		
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

7) PE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

8) PG[M+NH₄]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PG	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	No
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH ₄] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator
Fragment name -HG(PG,172)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

8) PG[M+NH₄]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

9) PS[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PS	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	No
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator
Fragment name -HG(PS,185)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

9) PS[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

10) SM[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	SM	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	No
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator
Fragment name			
HG(PC,184)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

10) SM[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

11) TG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	TG	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	No
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator
Fragment name			
-FA1(+HO)-(NH3)			
-FA2(+HO)-(NH3)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

11) TG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-